

Exploring the external resource generation strategies of secondary public schools in San Luis, Pampanga

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Abstract

The study aims to explore the resource generation strategies employed by secondary public schools in San Luis, Pampanga. The present study involved 33 respondents from the public secondary schools in San Luis, Pampanga during the school year 2023-2024. For this study, a probability sampling technique was used. In addition, in this study, a custom-designed digital questionnaire was created as a researcher-made instrument. The questionnaire was distributed using Google Forms. To analyze the collected data, the researchers employed a combination of descriptive statistical methods, median, and interquartile range. The data indicates that grants and donations are perceived as the most successful external resource generation strategy by respondent school staff, followed by partnerships and linkages, fundraising events, resource sharing, and social welfare programs. Respondents agree that there are hindrances in generating additional resources from external sources. Difficulties include identifying the correct platform for fundraisers, reaching the right audience, constrained ability of other government agencies to help, short-term nature of grants and donations, distrust between schools and private industries, disagreements over shared resources, and sustainability difficulties of shared resources over time

Keywords: Resource generation; Probability; Partnerships; Linkages

1. Introduction

In the pursuit of quality education, secondary public schools face the critical challenge of resource mobilization. These institutions rely not only on government funding but also on external resources to enhance their programs, facilities, and overall effectiveness. Understanding the strategies employed by schools in generating these external resources is essential for sustainable development and equitable educational opportunities.

This study aims to delve into the multifaceted landscape of resource acquisition, utilization, and accountability within secondary public schools in San Luis, Pampanga. By examining the various approaches schools adopt, the researchers can identify best practices, address gaps, and foster community engagement. Ultimately, this research contributes to informed decision-making and the improvement of educational outcomes for students.

In the Philippines, school-based management plays a pivotal role in shaping the quality of education. Central to this approach is the provision of direct funding to schools, enabling them to meet their operational needs effectively. Over the past five years, the government's commitment to strengthening school-based management has been evident through a substantial increase—45 percent in real terms—in funds allocated directly to schools. These funds primarily support maintenance and other operating expenses (MOOE), empowering schools to implement their improvement

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plans autonomously. The recent surge in direct funding underscores the government's recognition of schools' essential role in educational development. By channeling resources directly to schools, the aim is to enhance their capacity to provide quality education. The increase in MOOE funding signifies a shift toward greater autonomy for schools. Rather than relying solely on centralized decisions, schools now have the means to address their unique needs and priorities.

However, each school faces distinct challenges. The government's commitment extends beyond mere financial support. Schools were being encouraged to tailor their improvement plans based on local context, student demographics, and community dynamics. In addition, schools must demonstrate transparent utilization of resources, ensuring that every peso contributes to student learning outcomes.

A common goal of educational reforms is to create new school dynamics (Robinson & Aronica, 2015). School administrators have faced a growing number of financial constraints in recent years. A few of these are the quantity of students in a class, the pay and hours worked by teachers, the caliber of their educational output, the practice of giving resources to some students but not to others, and the relationship between resources and accomplishments (Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development, 2015). The management is crucial to the implementation of education reform, even as it works to uphold its own goals and principles (Patterson et al., 2013) and takes into account the unique features and conditions of the school (Schechter & Shaked, 2017). School principals and policy makers can identify the powers, fears, constrictions, and coping strategies involved in managerial decision-making in schools by understanding the various patterns of decision-making and the underlying mindset of the principals. This will help them be aware of these processes when creating and implementing educational policies for schools.

The study conducted by Tamir, Emanuel, and Arar (2019) delved into the decision-making processes of Israeli high school leaders during the implementation of the "Courage to Change" reform. The reform aimed to respond to public demands for improving the education system. It provided schools with additional resources in the form of "weekly instruction time." Qualitative analysis based on interviews with staff from nineteen high schools revealed three decision-making patterns among managerial staff. The study contributes to the theory of incremental decisions in schools. It aligned with the Institutional Approach, emphasizing how schools allocate non-financial resources. The findings inform schools facing similar resource allocation tasks. Understanding these decision-making patterns can guide effective policy implementation.

When it comes to allocating resources, school administrators and management personnel sometimes feel pressured to find ways to take advantage of more resources, like more teachers, almost at any cost. As a result, their decisions tend to be more situation-oriented than need-oriented because they lack the time to give the process the careful consideration it needs (Author & Other, 2018). Establishing a committee with outside experts who are not employed by the school is one of the strategies used by school administrators to gain public legitimacy and secure additional funding, even though the committee's work may lead to criticism of the institution regarding the dialogue that is fostered between educators, students, and parents (Turner & Spain, 2016).

Better organizational administrators, in the opinion of Ikediugwu (2016), should carefully and appropriately manage school resources, including capital, supplies, equipment, and e-learning resources like computers, educational technology, and internal infrastructure, entrusted to them for appropriate financial management. All available resources—human, material, financial, and physical—must be managed skillfully if education is to succeed. Effective planning, budgeting, allocating, and control of all the resources used by the organization are necessary to achieve this.

On the other hand, Usman (2016) stated that in order to minimize costs and raise the caliber of teaching and learning in the classroom, the education system must include the following requirements in order to actualize academic goals and objectives: adequate resource provision, full utilization, and proper handling of educational resource objectives. In order to accomplish educational goals and objectives, managing school resources means making the most of all available resources. It provides and arranges for the full and efficient use of all required resources.

Meanwhile, Maritan and Lee (2017) asserted that the formulation of a strategy requires the allocation of resources, but unlike in the educational sector, there is a dearth of literature, particularly when it comes to the allocation of financial, material, technological, and human resources that support the firm's plans. Since resource allocation processors affect and are influenced by most other operations in educational institutions, research on these processors is especially important. There are enormous aspects that need to be considered in resource allocation for education. The problem of allocating resources to academic institutions is multi-faceted (Etor, Ekanem, and Sule, 2020).

Furthermore, both contexts emphasize the importance of resource utilization. Effective education requires full utilization of available resources, whether it's for teaching and learning in classrooms or for overall organizational

success. Maritan and Lee (2017) highlight the need for strategic resource allocation in educational institutions. Similarly, decision-makers in schools must allocate resources strategically to achieve academic goals and objectives. Etor, Ekanem, and Sule (2020) mention the multi-faceted nature of resource allocation in academic institutions. Similarly, decision-making processes involve considering various aspects, including curriculum policies, implementation strategies, evaluation procedures, and research activities.

In view of this, the need to study the external resource generation strategies of secondary public schools in San Luis, Pampanga is significant. Schools often face financial limitations, affecting their ability to provide quality education. Understanding effective resource generation strategies can help schools overcome these constraints. Studying resource generation, policymakers can ensure that resources are allocated fairly across schools. Currently, better-off schools tend to receive a larger share of intended funds, leaving others underserved. Evidence shows that increased funding and effective school-based management lead to better education outcomes. Implementing successful resource strategies can positively impact student performance. Strengthening accountability mechanisms associated with resource use is crucial. Addressing weaknesses in managing funds at the school and community levels can significantly enhance education outcomes.

Objectives of the Study

General Objective

The study aims to explore the resource generation strategies employed by secondary public schools in San Luis, Pampanga.

Specific Objectives:

- To identify the different external resource generation strategies employed by secondary public schools in San Luis, Pampanga;
- To assess the level of effectiveness of the different external resource generation strategies in supplementing their funding requirement;
- To investigate the main obstacles that hinder the process of generating additional resources in the study areas;
- To develop innovative strategies and funding models that ensure the sustainable resource generation efforts of secondary public schools in San Luis, Pampanga.

2. Methodology

The present study involved 33 respondents from the public secondary schools in San Luis, Pampanga during the school year 2023-2024. The research used quantitative descriptive research design. It is also referred to as descriptive statistics research approach that entails the collection and analysis of numerical data to depict and summarize a specific phenomenon or population. Its primary objective is to present a holistic overview of a situation or occurrence by examining the frequency, distribution, and patterns of the variables being studied. This method often utilizes surveys, questionnaires, or other data collection tools to gather information from a representative sample of participants (Cohen, Manion & Morrison 2018).

For this study, a probability sampling technique was used. It is a process of selecting respondents in which all members of the entire population are given a chance of being selected as samples. Using probability sampling, the researcher can choose a sample, or a subset of the population, at random for the research. Another name for it is random sampling. Every research unit—that is, every individual, company, or organization in your population—must have an equal chance of being chosen in order for the study to be considered random. (Cristobal and Dela Cruz-Cristobal 2013). The respondents are faculty president of the school, PTA officers, and Adopt-A-School Program (ASP) Coordinator.

The respondents represent key stakeholders within the school community. The faculty president represents the teaching staff, the PTA officers represent parents and guardians, and the ASP Coordinator is directly involved in resource mobilization efforts. Including these specific roles, the study can gather comprehensive insights into resource generation strategies. The faculty president can provide perspectives on academic needs, the PTA officers can share community expectations, and the ASP Coordinator can offer insights into external partnerships. These respondents are often involved in decision-making related to resource allocation, fundraising, and community engagement. Their experiences and perspectives can inform effective strategies for resource generation. Considering both internal (faculty) and external (ASP) stakeholders ensures a holistic understanding of resource challenges and opportunities. This approach aligns with the study's goal of exploring various strategies.

In addition, in this study, a custom-designed digital questionnaire was created as a researcher-made instrument. The questionnaire was distributed using Google Forms. To ensure the relevance and accuracy of the instrument, the researchers approached the three experts comprising of Education Program Supervisor in English, Research Instructor and a statistician to assess its content validity. These experts reviewed the items and questions in the questionnaire to ensure they effectively capture and represent the content domain or construct under investigation.

Prior to implementing the instrument with the intended respondents, the instrument was pilot tested to the select division personnel to identify any uncertainties, challenges, or deficiencies in the wording or structure of the instrument. Valuable feedback obtained from the pilot test participants were utilized to make necessary adjustments and enhancements to the instrument, ensuring its clarity and effectiveness.

Similarly, the result of the pilot testing was subjected to Cronbach Alpha. The results showed that all expert validators rated all the items of the instrument to be highly relevant to the variables they intend to measure, the constructs they are in, as well as with the study as a whole, passing the validity test with a content validity index of 1.00. Moreover, the instrument passed in terms of internal reliability, with all constructs garnering Cronbach's alpha values that exceed 0.70. With the establishment of the research instruments' validity and reliability. With that, the tool was used for the accurate and reliable data collection and measurement. To analyze the collected data, the researchers employed a combination of descriptive statistical such frequency, mean and standard deviation.

3. Results and Discussion

The study aims to explore the resource generation strategies employed by secondary public schools in San Luis, Pampanga. Presented below are the results of the data based on the objectives presented in the introduction.

3.1. External resource generation strategies employed by secondary public schools.

Table 1 External resource generation strategies employed by secondary public schools.

External resource generation strategies	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Description	Interpretation
Grants and Donations				
Seeking financial support through grants from government agencies, private foundations, and corporations.	3.81	1.03	Often	Implemented
Encouraging donations from alumni, local businesses, and community members.	4.19	0.74	Often	Implemented
Overall	4.00	0.91	Often	Implemented
Partnerships and Linkages	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Description	Interpretation
Collaborating with businesses, non-profits, and other educational institutions to gain access to additional resources.	3.63	0.94	Often	Implemented
Securing sponsorships or educational funding from companies that are interested in supporting education.	3.28	0.89	Sometimes	Moderately Implemented
Overall	3.45	0.92	Often	Implemented
Fundraising Events	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Description	Interpretation
Facilitating sport events like fun runs with the aim of fundraising for school endeavors.	3.19	1.31	Sometimes	Moderately Implemented
Conducting galas or personal development nights as avenues for fundraising for the school community.	3.34	1.18	Sometimes	Moderately Implemented

Overall	3.27	1.24	Sometimes	Moderately Implemented
Resource Sharing	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Description	Interpretation
Sharing resources with other schools or educational institutions to reduce costs and increase efficiency (i.e sports fields, auditoriums)	2.91	1.17	Sometimes	Moderately Implemented
Facilitating a dynamic exchange of knowledge by inviting esteemed educators from various institutions to lead workshops and training sessions, thereby fostering a rich environment for professional growth and development among peers.	3.78	1.07	Often	Implemented
Overall	3.34	1.20	Sometimes	Moderately Implemented
Social Welfare Programs	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Description	Interpretation
Collaborating with the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD) on projects aligned with their objectives.	3.28	1.02	Sometimes	Moderately Implemented
Partnering with the Department of Science and Technology (DOST) for programs promoting science and technology education.	2.53	1.11	Seldom	Less Implemented
Working with the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) for welfare programs supporting higher education institutions (HEIs).	2.50	1.32	Seldom	Less Implemented
Overall	2.77	1.20	Sometimes	Moderately Implemented

According to the preceding table, schools tend to generate resources externally from various sources with varying degrees and frequencies of implementation. Grants and donations ($\mu = 4.00$) are implemented the most, with the respondents affirming that they often generate external resources for the school by seeking financial support in the form of grants from government agencies, private foundations, and corporations ($\mu = 3.81$). Similarly, they often encourage donations from alumni, local enterprises, and community members ($\mu = 4.19$). Resource sharing ($\mu = 3.34$) is not as implemented as seeking for grants and donations but is still more frequently conducted than the other remaining external resource generation schemes. Schools often work with other educational institutions for knowledge exchange and professional growth development activities ($\mu = 3.78$). They sometimes share material resources and facilities with other academic institutions to reduce operating and maintenance costs, as well as to improve efficiency ($\mu = 2.91$). Meanwhile, partnerships and linkages and fundraising events are both implemented in moderation ($\mu = 3.45$). Schools moderately implement collaboration with businesses, non-profits, and other educational institutions to gain access to additional resources ($\mu = 3.63$).

Furthermore, they moderately facilitate securing of sponsorships from companies ($\mu = 3.28$). Additionally, setting up sport events like fun runs with the aim of fundraising for school endeavors ($\mu = 3.19$) are done moderately, while galas or personal development nights as avenues for fundraising for the school community are implemented more often ($\mu = 3.34$). Nevertheless, fundraising events are conducted in moderate frequency ($\mu = 3.34$). However, social welfare programs are the least preferred external resource generation strategy of the schools ($\mu = 2.77$). The respondents moderately collaborate with the Department of Social Welfare and Development in areas of overlaps in the agencies' responsibilities and objectives ($\mu = 3.28$). Moreover, collaborating with the Commission on Higher Education is implemented less than moderate ($\mu = 2.50$). Finally, schools seldomly work with the Department of Science and Technology for external resource generation ($\mu = 2.53$).

3.2. Assessment on the level of effectiveness of the different external resource generation strategies in supplementing their funding requirement

Table 2 Assessment on the level of effectiveness of the different external resource generation strategies in supplementing their funding requirement

Level of effectiveness of the different external resource generation strategies	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Description
Grants and donations enabled our schools to allocate specific funds for the renovation of existing classrooms, the construction of additional facilities, and the acquisition of advanced educational technology.	4.25	1.05	Very Effective
Our established partnerships and linkages help us fulfill immediate financial needs and also promotes enduring progress and expansion.	4.09	1.12	Sometimes Effective
Fundraising events that we organized act as critical support system to fulfill diverse resource and financial needs	4.16	0.85	Sometimes Effective
Resource sharing with other organizations enabled our school in leveraging with economies of scale, resulting in substantial cost savings.	3.66	0.94	Sometimes Effective
Social Welfare Programs provided essential support to our school through grants and subsidies for educational materials and technology.	3.72	0.85	Sometimes Effective
Overall	3.98	0.98	Sometimes Effective

The table above shows that the respondents find grants and donations as the most successful resource generation external source in achieving their fund-raising goals and producing the desired outcomes ($\mu = 4.25$). Partnerships and linkages ($\mu = 4.09$), fundraising events ($\mu = 4.16$), resource sharing ($\mu = 3.66$), and social welfare programs ($\mu = 3.72$) have been rated by the respondents as sometimes effective in accomplishing the intended results of their fund-generating ventures. Overall, the mentioned external resource generation strategies were found to be somewhat effective by respondent school staff ($\mu = 3.98$).

3.3. Obstacles that hinder the process of generating additional resources.

Table 3 Obstacles that hinder the process of generating additional resources.

Obstacles that hinder the process of generating additional resources.	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Description	Interpretation
Project-specific and short-term nature of grants and donations hindered the alignment of our school's long-term strategic needs	3.25	0.84	Moderately Agree	Moderately Encountered
Distrust or questioning each other's actions and intentions between the school and its partner industries and organizations are experience.	3.00	1.24	Moderately Agree	Moderately Encountered
Trust issues, suspicion and lack of cooperation resulted to oversight and accountability.	3.22	1.21	Moderately Agree	Moderately Encountered
Problems of finding the correct platform to host the fundraiser and reaching the right audience.	3.59	0.91	Agree	Encountered
Disagreements over shared resources lead to conflicts, and detrimental to the collective goals.	3.25	1.19	Moderately Agree	Moderately Encountered
Ensuring the sustainability of shared resources over time is difficult, and exhaustible specifically when ongoing maintenance, infrastructures or repairs in school.	3.41	1.10	Agree	Moderately Encountered

7. Social welfare programs face budget constraints, limiting their ability to allocate sufficient funds	3.66	0.97	Agree	Encountered
Overall	3.34	1.10	Moderately Agree	Moderately Encountered

Based on the preceding table, the respondents moderately agree that, overall, there are hindrances in the process of generating additional resources from external sources ($\mu = 3.34$). However, the respondents agree that identifying the correct platform to host fundraisers and reaching the right audience ($\mu = 3.59$), ensuring the sustainability of shared resources over time ($\mu = 3.41$), as well as the constrained ability of other government agencies to help ($\mu = 3.66$) are the income generating difficulties that they encounter. Struggles about the short-term nature of grants and donations ($\mu = 3.25$), distrust between schools and private industries ($\mu = 3.00$), lack of accountability ($\mu = 3.22$), disagreements over shared resources ($\mu = 3.25$), were not as high, with the users only moderately agreeing that they encountered these hindrance.

The collected data indicates that grants and donations are the predominant methods of external resource generation for schools. Respondents frequently engage in procuring financial support through grants from government entities, private foundations, and corporations. This trend underscores the effectiveness of innovative strategies and funding models in bolstering the sustainability of resource generation for secondary public schools in San Luis, Pampanga. Consequently, these practices are poised to serve as a benchmark for the school to maintain and enhance its external resource generation initiatives.

This suggests that grants and donations are the most effective methods for generating external resources in schools. This is evidenced by the active pursuit of financial support from various sectors, including government agencies, private foundations, and corporations. Such a trend highlights the efficacy of innovative strategies and funding models that contribute to the sustainable development of resource generation for secondary public schools in San Luis, Pampanga. These methods are set to become a model for continuous improvement in external resource generation.

In the context of Stakeholder Theory, which posits that organizations should account for the interests of all stakeholders beyond just shareholders, this approach is particularly relevant. By involving local businesses and organizations, schools can generate value for the wider community, which is in harmony with the principles of Stakeholder Theory. This theory is aptly suited for the current study as it emphasizes the importance of creating shared value through stakeholder engagement.

Similarly, the Resource-Based Theory underscores the importance of acquiring and managing valuable resources to secure a competitive edge. The proactive procurement of grants and awards is in line with this theory, as it entails the gathering of resources that are instrumental in fostering educational innovation and sustainability. This theory is fitting for the study as it focuses on leveraging unique resources to build a distinctive advantage in the educational landscape.

Resource generation in schools directly impacts student learning outcomes and overall educational quality. By investing in high-quality educational materials and equitable distribution of resources, schools can create an environment conducive to effective teaching and student success. In the context of **secondary schools in San Luis, Pampanga**, strategic measures and innovative approaches are essential for sustaining resource generation. Prioritize educational goals, teacher needs, and student outcomes when making resource allocation decisions. Create budgets and oversee spending to ensure the long-term sustainability of programs. Communicate effectively with parents and guardians. Building strong relationships with stakeholders can lead to better resource support and collaboration. Align resource management strategies with the mission and vision of the whole school community. Optimize resource use by involve key school and community leaders in shaping a vision for improving schools through open, credible processes. Connect with other schools to share ideas, learn from successes, and collaborate on resource generation strategies. Effective resource management is critical for providing quality education to students. By implementing these strategies, schools can enhance their ability to allocate resources wisely, improve facilities, and provide necessary materials for student success.

4. Discussion

The research used quantitative descriptive research design and utilized the data gathering through google form in order to explore the resource generation strategies employed by secondary public schools in San Luis, Pampanga.

A methodical investigation of the school's internal and external environments that guides strategic managerial decision-making is known as strategic analysis. Strategic analysis, one of the main components of the strategic planning process, gives the stakeholders in the school a clear understanding of what they have to work with and what needs to be addressed when creating a plan for the school's success by allowing them to examine the internal and external school environmental factors. School managers require the information generated by strategic analysis to create effective plans for their school's success. Notably, a sound strategy should make advantage of the school's assets and competencies to establish a position that will allow it to effectively accomplish its long-term goals.

Based on the literature studies mentioned in the introduction of this paper, educational reforms and decision-making patterns intersect in resource allocation, balancing priorities, implementation strategies, and responsiveness to external influences. They highlighted that both educational reforms and decision-making in schools involve resource allocation. Reforms often aim to address resource constraints, such as class size, teacher pay, and student support. Similarly, school administrators make decisions about allocating resources (e.g., staffing, funding) to meet educational goals. In both contexts, decision-makers must balance competing priorities. Educational reforms seek to improve outcomes while managing limited resources. School principals face similar challenges when distributing resources to various programs, students, and staff. The study by Tamir, Emanuel, and Arar (2019) highlighted decision-making patterns during the implementation of the "Courage to Change" reform. Similarly, effective educational reforms require thoughtful implementation strategies to achieve desired outcomes. Both reforms and school decisions are influenced by external factors. Reforms respond to public demands, while schools consider community expectations and external funding sources (e.g., committees with outside experts).

The findings from the data provided previously explains that in terms of **External Resource Generation Strategies**, schools are finding different ways to get extra resources from outside their usual budget. They mostly get these resources through grants and donations, which they get quite often. This means they regularly ask for money from places like government offices, private groups, and companies, and they also get a lot of help from former students, local businesses, and people in the community. Sharing resources with other schools happens too, but not as much as getting grants and donations. This sharing is usually about swapping knowledge and helping each other grow professionally. Sometimes, schools also share things like equipment and buildings to save money and be more efficient. Partnerships and fundraising events happen a fair amount. Schools work with businesses and other organizations to get more resources, and they also run events like sports days and fancy dinners to raise money. These events happen regularly, but not all the time. However, schools do not really utilize social welfare programs to get resources. They only sometimes work with social welfare departments when they have common goals. Working with higher education and science and technology departments is even less common.

In terms of Effectiveness of **Strategies**, the results suggests that school staff find receiving grants and donations to be the most helpful way to meet their fundraising targets and achieve what they aim for with those funds. Other methods like forming partnerships, holding fundraising events, sharing resources, and conducting social welfare programs also contribute to reaching their financial goals, but to a lesser extent compared to grants and donations. As a whole, these strategies are considered fairly effective by the staff in supporting the school's fundraising efforts.

In terms of Obstacles that hinder the process of generating additional resources, overall, respondents agree that there are hindrances in generating additional resources from external sources. Difficulties include identifying the correct platform for fundraisers, reaching the right audience, constrained ability of other government agencies to help, short-term nature of grants and donations, distrust between schools and private industries, disagreements over shared resources, and sustainability difficulties of shared resources over time.

This also indicates that school staff generally feel there are some obstacles when trying to get extra funds from outside sources. They particularly find it challenging to choose the right platforms for fundraising activities and to connect with the appropriate audience. They also face issues in maintaining the long-term availability of resources that are shared and feel that there is limited support from other government bodies. While they do encounter problems like the temporary nature of grants and donations, mistrust with private sectors, accountability issues, and conflicts over resource sharing, these are seen as less significant compared to the other challenges mentioned.

In essence, schools in San Luis Pampanga employ a variety of external resource generation strategies, with grants and donations being the most common. While these strategies are somewhat effective, schools face challenges related to resource generation. Identifying effective platforms for fundraising and addressing obstacles are crucial for sustainable resource management.

In terms of resource management challenge, both educational administrators and decision-makers face challenges related to resource management. Administrators must skillfully manage various resources (capital, supplies, equipment, e-learning tools) entrusted to them, while decision-makers allocate resources (human, material, financial, physical) within schools.

Material and physical resources refers to educational resources that support instructional procedures and methods. Examples of these resources include buildings, science and computer labs, libraries, technological facilities, teaching materials, furniture and fixtures, classrooms, offices, school records and documentation, and sports facilities. Material or physical resource management is the process of using educational resources and infrastructure in an effective and efficient way to improve an institution. Akinfolarin and Ehinola (2014) state that school facilities should be maintained in order to support effective teaching and knowledge delivery that promotes academic performance. Institutional infrastructures are the most important factor influencing both the high standard of education provided by teachers and the academic achievements of students at any given school. Material resource management, on the other hand, is critical to the school system, as incompetent management can reduce the effectiveness of educational results.

The effectiveness of school resource management, according to Nurkolis & Sulisworo (2018), is measured by how well management objectives are met and how well educators, infrastructure, and other resources are used to accomplish school objectives and create a supportive learning environment where the community can benefit from the outputs of the schools.

As a result, resource planning—a critical part of efficient financial management—must be done by schools. Resource planning is the process of locating and allocating resources in a higher education establishment. It includes both short- and long-term plans. It includes things like financial management, human resources, and annual budgeting. The output of these processes is the creation of budgetary allotments for each unit within an organization. Resource planning that aligns the financial, human, material, and physical resources of the school with its objectives and needs, both now and in the future. When this process is carried out properly, an organization can start new projects and continue with its essential ongoing initiatives. Stakeholders would also understand how and why choices are made if they are made transparently.

The process of resource planning is never-ending. While there may be some variation within institutions, it may be appropriate to adjust estimations and best prepare for organizational requirements at the appropriate time to verify the status of finances on a monthly, quarterly, or annual basis. Specific industrial cycles and national school funding procedures may influence requirements. Institutions must generally prioritize actions that support their main objectives and find a comfortable balance between spending and ongoing obligations.

An essential part of good financial management is creating a budget. The budget acts as a tool for monitoring spending over the course of the year and outlines how resources will be distributed. It offers a uniform framework that makes it possible for all parties involved to understand how the school's expenditure affects the accomplishment of its objectives and other goals. Plans for the school may be created by administrators, but if they are not supported by funding, they risk failing. Institutions can only allocate resources appropriately through financing. Therefore, there must be a clear connection between the school's annual budget and improvement strategy. Proper budgeting means staying out of debt but also not having large amounts of money left over at the end of the year unless there is a very good reason to. This involves considering how the spending plan for a certain category of purchases will stabilize over a time frame other than the upcoming fiscal year. Since they are an integral part of the organization and actively participate in the operation of the entire program, individuals working in the school system should always be considered when creating the budget.

The ability of the educational system to maximize the added value of input variables and generate the highest possible output is referred to as quality of education. According to this interpretation, the ability of education in schools to meet standards and accomplish goals is included in the quality of education. Effective resource management in schools can lead to improvements in educational quality.

Both human and non-human resources are available to the school in this situation. Education personnel, instructors, and school principals are examples of these human resources. Infrastructure, the environment, educational initiatives, and other programs are examples of non-human resources. One of the core problems in managing other school resources is the study of school effectiveness in situational leadership. This is so because the principle is in charge of situational leadership at the school. It is the principal's duty to bring together and persuade a group of educators to collaborate toward the school's objectives.

According to the principal's role, all school activities, including technical ones and some programs, are under their control. They manage the school's resources to ensure that objectives are met. Principals have the ability to design specific programs that help the school reach its objectives while also raising the standard of instruction. These initiatives may take the shape of collaboration initiatives, initiatives to enhance student and teacher quality, or initiatives to promote learning. Infrastructure and facilities at schools are among the resources available to them to raise the standard of instruction. One of the things that helps schools achieve their objectives is the provision of infrastructure for schools. In order to accomplish school objectives, infrastructure in this instance consists of equipment and learning support equipment. The accomplishment of goals, the availability of infrastructure, the appropriate use of media, and the discussion of material are all considered markers of an infrastructure facility's effectiveness in usage.

One of the most essential human resource roles in fostering a positive learning environment is that of educators and education professionals. In this instance, educators are teachers, while education staff consists of other non-teaching staff members and administrative personnel. Teachers and other education staff that uphold standards and carry out their responsibilities efficiently will design a learning process that aligns with the objectives of the school. The academic output of the school demonstrates qualities of a good school. Effective resource management in schools yields characteristics in students that align with school objectives, leading to good output. The accomplishments of students in both academic and extracurricular domains serve as an illustration of school output.

The findings from the tables suggest that schools are actively seeking external resources, with grants and donations being the primary and most effective methods. This indicates a strong reliance on external financial support, which can be both beneficial and challenging. The impact of this reliance is multifaceted. The successful acquisition of grants and donations can lead to improved educational facilities, resources, and opportunities for students and staff. Encouraging donations from alumni and local businesses fosters a sense of community involvement and investment in the school's success. Collaborations with other institutions for knowledge exchange can enhance the professional development of educators.

However, the dependence on external funding raises questions about the long-term sustainability of these resources, especially if they are subject to the short-term nature of grants. Identifying appropriate fundraising platforms and audiences, as well as maintaining shared resources, can be operationally challenging and time-consuming. The constrained ability of government agencies to assist may limit the scope of resources schools can access.

Schools may need to diversify their resource generation strategies to reduce over-reliance on any single source. Efforts to build trust between schools and private industries could open up new avenues for resource generation. Addressing issues of accountability could enhance the effectiveness of partnerships and resource sharing. While schools are making headway in generating external resources, there is room for improvement in terms of strategy diversification, operational efficiency, and building sustainable partnerships. Addressing these areas could lead to more stable and reliable resource generation, ultimately benefiting the educational environment and its stakeholders. It also underscores the importance of strategic planning and relationship management in the context of school resource generation.

5. Conclusions

Based on the data gathered, the following are the conclusions of the study.

- That schools are actively engaging in various strategies to generate resources from external sources. The most common and effective method is through grants and donations, which they often seek from a range of sources including government, private foundations, and corporations, as well as from alumni and the local community. Resource sharing with other educational institutions is also a frequent practice, though not as prevalent as grants and donations. Collaborations for additional resources and sponsorships, as well as fundraising events like sports activities and galas, are moderately used strategies. However, social welfare programs and partnerships with certain government departments are less commonly utilized.
- That schools consider grants and donations as the most effective means of external resource generation for achieving their fundraising objectives and desired outcomes. Other strategies like forming partnerships, organizing fundraising events, sharing resources, and engaging in social welfare programs are also beneficial, but to a lesser degree.
- That schools recognize challenges in generating additional resources from external sources, certain issues stand out more than others. The most significant difficulties they face include finding the right platforms for fundraising, reaching the intended audience, ensuring the ongoing availability of shared resources, and limited

assistance from other government agencies. Although concerns like the temporary nature of grants, mistrust with private sectors, accountability, and disagreements over resources are acknowledged, they are not viewed as the primary obstacles.

- That schools can draw on the principles of Stakeholder Theory and Resource-Based Theory, in its effort on external resource generation and to in order to align well with broader strategic and ethical considerations.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions, the following are recommended.

- **For Identifying External Resource Generation Strategies**
- Conduct a comprehensive survey of local businesses, alumni, and community organizations to catalog potential sources of grants and donations.
- Establish a database of external resource opportunities, including details on application processes, deadlines, and requirements.
- **For Assessing Effectiveness of Strategies**
- Implement a tracking system to monitor the outcomes of each resource generation initiative, measuring both financial impact and community engagement.
- Regularly review and analyze the performance of different strategies to identify the most cost-effective and impactful approaches.
- **For Investigating Obstacles in Resource Generation:**
- Organize focus group discussions with school staff and stakeholders to gather insights into the challenges faced during fundraising efforts.
- Develop a feedback mechanism where staff can report issues in real-time, allowing for quicker identification and resolution of obstacles.
- **For Developing Innovative Strategies and Funding Models**
- Explore partnerships with local government units and private sectors to create joint ventures that can provide steady funding streams.
- Investigate the feasibility of income-generating projects, such as school-based enterprises or rental of school facilities, that align with educational goals.

General Recommendations

Foster a culture of innovation within the school community, encouraging staff to propose new ideas for resource generation.

Provide professional development opportunities focused on grant writing, fundraising strategies, and partnership management.

Engage in strategic planning sessions with stakeholders to align resource generation efforts with the long-term vision of the schools.

Compliance with ethical standards

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